

On Volume 1 of Schreber's Fantastic Mammal

Tomoyuki Inaba

Institute for Live Fossils

abstract

Sherborn (1891) gives the date of publication of Schreber's Mammal vol. 1 as [1774] with a bracket. This means that it is an inference by Sherborn, and later Poche (1911) also made a similar judgment. In both cases, the original documents at the time of publication could not be confirmed. It is based on, the description of Allgemeine Literaturzeitung. Revision der Literatur für die Jahre 1785 - 1800 (1801), which states that "publishing began in the year following 1773," and Wrede and Weber (1806), "From 1774 (publishing)." From the wrapping paper at the time of publication, which they were not able to refer to this time, we were able to confirm that the magazine was published in eight monthly installments, beginning with the combined issues of January and February in 1774. The August issue, which is the 7th separate volume, contains a notice dated October 10 in which the text of the first volume will be published with the title and preface in the September issue, and that the first volume will be completed has been written. From November 1, 1774, which is written in the preface, it is highly possible that the final eighth volume could have been published within 1774. On the other hand, as for the illustrations, in the May issue Schreber wrote to the readers that illustrations #10 and #20 have not yet been published, "Die zehente und fünf und zwanzigste Kupfertafel müssen wir noch schuldig bleiben." In the combined January and February issue, #10 was written as being in preparation, but #20 was an illustration that should have been published in the March issue. Also, in the September issue, which is the eighth and final issue of Volume 1, it is written that illustrations #10 and #60 have not yet been published. This paper summarizes the first volume based on the materials at the time of the first issue.